
D3.6 Proposed harmonised verification framework for quality checking EPC outputs

Task 3.4 Verification and control

WP3 Deriving Technical Guidelines for EPCs

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Work Package 3 of the crossCert project primarily focuses on technical analysis of the results of the cross-testing of sample buildings across different EPC methodologies. Alongside a wider review into the various EPC methodologies and frameworks in use by partner countries, this work identifies how different EPC approaches are in Europe and the consequences of this. The current report uses the collected information of EPC frameworks to highlight the differences and best practices in quality control mechanisms across the crossCert countries, and proposes a framework for the harmonisation of such practices to encourage more robust mechanisms. The primary objective of this report is to examine the critical aspects of Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) assessments that can influence quality control and how these can be utilised to standardise quality control across different European countries.

In order to achieve our objective, this report relies on the data collected from the C-testing and L-testing reports in Work Package 2 (see Deliverable D2.4). We have also taken into account the feedback received from project partners through questionnaires for D3.1. Furthermore, information gathered from partners as part of Work Packages 4 and 5 (D4.2 and D5.3 deliverables, respectively) has been utilised in this report. We have also considered similar projects' findings, including QualDeEPC, XTendo, and the Concerted Action EPBD reports.

The findings of the previous work in Work Package 3 reveal significant differences in various aspects of EPC assessments in crossCert countries, including the calculation methodology, EPC software, EPC document itself, and the required qualifications of assessors. This report focuses on these aspects as factors that can play a crucial role in the quality control of EPCs and proposes a framework that can be applied to any EPC methodology in order to establish the main features of quality control mechanisms.

Whilst creating the quality control framework demonstrates the pathways that the studied countries follow, it simultaneously demonstrates that quality control is not administered in a harmonised way. Some countries are found to rely more on automatic quality control and error-checking at the accredited software level, whereas other countries use the national lodgement database of EPCs as a checkpoint. The extent that these control procedures are used at all, and the type of body that oversees this process, also varies by country. Furthermore, albeit from only a select number (nine) of partner countries, there does not seem to be a correlation between quality control procedures and the type of assessor workforce running the EPCs within a given country.

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1 Introduction

Quality control of EPCs is essential to make EPCs robust and reliable. Since EPCs are compliance tools designed mainly for comparison between buildings, EPCs are not necessarily intended to reflect the actual operation of the building. Instead, they should be able to reflect the energy performance of the assessed building and its systems for a typical, assumed operation. Depending on the EPC calculation methodology, the reliability of the EPC can be assessed by evaluating input data, output data and energy efficiency recommendations. Such evaluations can be carried out through different mechanisms. Performing random independent checks, as prescribed by Article 18 of the EPBD (EPBD, 2018), is the main tool countries use for quality control of EPCs. Targeted controls to check the correct application of the different instruments and compliance with different requirements are also used across some countries to ensure high-quality certificates (Loncour and Roelens, 2015). These steps can be complemented by implementing low-cost measures such as using validation rules in the calculation software or applying consistency checks to the central EPC databases to avoid faulty certificates. The differences between methodologies determine the emphasis on specific quality control steps in each country's holistic quality control mechanism.

Details of the EPC calculation methodology, such as the complexity level, the number of inputs, data collection methods, and use of default values and look-up tables, can all impact the quality of EPCs and, in turn, the framework used for quality control. In addition, the level of reliance on the assessors' knowledge in providing energy efficiency recommendations can increase or decrease the possibility of error and impact the quality control protocols. Some methodologies use pre-defined energy efficiency recommendations, whereas others leave it entirely up to the assessor to suggest measures to improve the EPC rating of the building. In such cases, and in general, assessor training plays a crucial role in EPC quality for all methodologies. This is particularly true in methodologies where the assessor has a more prominent role. Furthermore, with the emergence of next-generation metrics, the quality control protocols have to consider the specific properties of those assessment methodologies and be able to adapt to those as well.

As discussed in detail in other crossCert reports (Sayfekar and Jenkins, 2022, 2023), there are significant differences in calculation methodologies and software, approaches to energy efficiency recommendations, and requirements for assessor education and training across European countries. While general principles can be applied broadly, a quality control system should account for the specific methodologies used in each country. This report highlights the differences between crossCert countries in each aspect and discusses potential best practice approaches.

2 Quality control mechanisms

2.1 Validation rules in the calculation software

Implementing validation rules in EPC software is recommended by previous studies as the first step in the quality control of EPCs (Loncour and Roelens, 2015; Mariottini, 2015; Roelens, Loncour and Antinucci, 2015; Jonathan Volt *et al.*, 2020). Applying validation rules in calculation software provides a cost effective and simple approach that can considerably influence the errors in EPC calculations. A study by BPIE (Roelens, Loncour and Antinucci, 2015) suggests using robust validation rules in the EPC software can even replace the manual check prescribed in Annex II of the EPBD. Examples of validation rules include detecting out of range or impossible values, and consistency checks (e.g. fan energy consumption in a naturally ventilated space) (Loncour and Roelens, 2015). Denmark, the UK, Greece, Slovenia and Malta are examples of crossCert countries where validation rules are implemented in EPC software. In the UK iSBEM software, the software doesn't warn the user about out of range values when entering the values. However, after running the calculations, it returns an error log, highlighting out-of-range values (for example, a wall U-value of 70). In addition, the software doesn't allow the user to navigate away from a record unless all of its necessary input parameters have been defined. Many parameters have default values embedded in the software. However, some values, such as the area of solar collectors, are necessary to run the calculations. In these cases, the user will receive an error message if they try to advance to the next stage without

defining all the necessary parameters. In Denmark, robust input parameter validation measures have been implemented in the EPC software since 2019 to prevent the entry of incorrect or unlikely values during EPC calculation (Thomsen *et al.*, 2020). The Slovenian software is also equipped with validation rules for building envelope or technical systems parameters and notifies the user of any out-of-range values. In case of missing inputs, the software uses default values instead. In the Austrian software, Gebäudeprofi, the assessor has access to the list of errors and explanations about them. However, testing the Austrian software for entering out-of-range values as part of the crossCert L-building tests for thermal conductivity and pump power didn't return any errors. Similarly, even though there are checks on inputs and results in place for the Croatian software, the software didn't highlight any out of range values. Only for missing data and for the building envelope parameters, when not in line with regulation, does the software issue a warning. In the Bulgarian EPC software, only some input fields have limits for the input value. Still, since the range permitted is very wide, this feature doesn't sufficiently contribute to validation checks. In the Spanish software CE3X, limited validation measures (primarily focused on missing inputs for the technical systems) are implemented, but the software doesn't prevent out-of-range values. For example, a U value of 0.0001 W/m²k and a 1 kg/m² density didn't return any warnings.

2.2 EPC database

Using EPC databases as a step in quality control provides an excellent low-cost opportunity for quality-checking EPCs (Roelens, Loncour and Antinucci, 2015). These databases are used for purposes including issuing certificates, quality control, cross-checking between various databases and statistical purposes. (Roelens, Loncour and Antinucci, 2015). All crossCert countries have set up databases for public or professional users' access. The crossCert Deliverable D4.2 investigated the current condition of these databases, their availability and the format of data across crossCert countries (Pedrosa and Fernández, 2023b).

Each crossCert country has a different approach towards using EPC databases. Some countries require more detailed inputs for lodging EPCs than others, creating more potential for the database to be used for more accurate quality controls in the future and for cross-checking information between several databases. For example, in Bulgaria, the assessors should upload the energy audit report, scanned copies of signed and stamped EPC certificates, and a summary of the energy audit in Microsoft Excel format. (Pedrosa and Fernández, 2023a). Similarly, Croatia requires many inputs, such as additional reports, the energy audit report and the EPC certificate. Also, in the UK and Spain (depending on the region), it is mandatory for the Energy Assessor Accreditation Schemes to lodge the underlying data used to produce the EPC certificate in addition to the PDF document (Junta de Castilla y León, 2018; Ministry of Housing, Communities and Local Government, 2021).

Similarly, countries vary in terms of applying quality control to their EPC databases. In some regions in Austria, the EPC database is used for quality checks (Gokarakonda *et al.*, 2020). In Bulgaria, the EPC database is not automatically checked. However, the certificates are checked by the experts in the Sustainable Energy Development Agency (SEDA) before being lodged in the database. In Croatia, there are no quality controls on the EPC database. In Denmark, the EPC database is equipped with automatic data validation (Gokarakonda *et al.*, 2020). When the EPC data is uploaded to the database, it is automatically compared to other building data. Also, there are ongoing analyses of error types in connection with using data in place. Greece also applies automatic validity checks on EPC data on the national EPC registry platform. In Malta, the database is owned by the Building Construction Agency (BCA), and the data is thoroughly checked and cleaned before being lodged (Government of Malta, 2021). In Poland, there is an automatic check for missing data in the EPC registry. However, there is no automatic check of the validity of EPC data. Proposals to improve the central register of EPCs are currently being prepared. Following their introduction, it will be possible to check the correctness of EPCs. In Slovenia, the electronic EPC registry runs an automatic check on the EPC certificates as well (Gokarakonda *et al.*, 2020). In Spain, there are variations between regions, but generally, some automatic quality checks are implemented in the EPC registry. For example, the automatic control measures implemented in the EPC database for the Castile

and León region include checks on various identifiers as well as the date of issue, the length of time between the site visit and EPC issue date, useful area, energy rating typology and any negative final energy values. In the UK, there are in-built validation rules within the Energy Performance of Buildings (EPB) register, which ensure that the XML file has been created by accredited software and that all fields are completed within set parameters and in the correct format. In addition, any values with correct formats that don't fall within the expected range will be flagged. Also, statistical analysis is performed on the registered EPCs for consistency and missing data and to ensure sensible trends across time (Ministry of Housing, Communities and Local Government, 2021).

2.3 Independent checks

Article 18 of the EPBD requires each member state to establish an independent control mechanism to ensure the quality of energy performance certificates. ANNEX II sets out the details of these controls as follows (EPBD, 2018):

"1. The competent authorities or bodies to which the competent authorities have delegated the responsibility for implementing the independent control system shall make a random selection of all the energy performance certificates issued annually and subject them to verification. The sample shall be of a sufficient size to ensure statistically significant compliance results.

The verification shall be based on the options indicated below or on equivalent measures:

(a) validity check of the input data of the building used to issue the energy performance certificate and the results stated in the certificate;

(b) check of the input data and verification of the results of the energy performance certificate, including the recommendations made;

(c) complete check of the input data of the building used to issue the energy performance certificate, complete verification of the results stated in the certificate, including the recommendations made, and on-site visit of the building, if possible, to check the correspondence between specifications given in the energy performance certificate and the building certified.

2. The competent authorities or bodies to which they have delegated the responsibility for implementing the independent control system shall randomly select at least a statistically significant percentage of all the inspection reports issued annually and verify those reports.

3- Where information is added to a database, it shall be possible for national authorities to identify the originator of the addition for monitoring and verification purposes."

Implementing independent controls on EPCs is required by the EPBD and it is carried out in all of the crossCert countries. However, there are variations amongst the countries regarding the organisation carrying out the controls and the scope of checks. In some countries, government bodies are in charge of quality controls and in others, third-party organisations (as authorised by the EPBD) perform the quality control checks. Some countries also use multiple levels of checks by third-party organisations and regulatory bodies in charge of EPCs. Differences also exist in the level of checks performed on the certificates (level a, b, c and c* (level c controls and site visits)).

The EPBD requires a statistically significant percentage of all EPCs to be randomly sampled to assess the overall quality of the EPCs or inspections. A confidence interval of 5% with a confidence level of 95% is considered suitable for this type of independent control. Randomly selecting a sample of EPCs ensures that the control results can be trusted to estimate the overall EPC quality accurately. Table 1 shows the required numbers according to Loncour and Roelens (2015).

In addition to the random sample controls, which mainly target assessments, targeted controls on assessors can also be implemented. In this type of control, instead of choosing a random sample of certificates to control, EPCs produced by specific assessors who are selected based on certain criteria (e.g. previously producing poor-quality EPCs, early career, etc.) are chosen to be checked (Loncour and

Roelens, 2015). This section summarises each crossCert country's approach to independent checks as advised by EPBD.

Table 1- Sample size for a statistically significant random sample (Loncour and Roelens, 2015)

Population	Sample size
100	80
200	132
500	217
1,000	278
1,000	322
5,000	357
10,000	370
20,000	377
50000	381
100,000	383
200,000	383
500000	384
1000000	384

2.4 Austria

About 3% of the uploaded EPCs are tested for plausibility and undergo random exact control and verification checks every year (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022). The controlling organisation is different in each province, and in some provinces, including the ZEUS-regions Burgenland, Kärnten, Salzburg, and Steiermark, the EPCs are controlled by the Energy Agencies. A complete control (level c), including occasional site visits, is used as the level of control (Gokarakonda *et al.*, 2020).

2.5 Bulgaria

In Bulgaria, the Sustainable Energy Development Agency (SEDA) is responsible for the quality control of EPCs. The building owner must send a copy of the EPC, a summary of the energy audit in standardised Excel format and the Energy Audit Report to SEDA electronically or manually. The experts in SEDA check the certificates and ask the EPC assessors to revise the EPCs. If the number of certificates arriving at the agency is high (e.g. when there is a financing program for building renovations), they usually check a sample of the documents. The control level applied is in line with the level c, and it includes occasional site-visits (Gokarakonda *et al.*, 2020).

2.6 Croatia

The Ministry of Physical Planning, Construction and State Assets establishes and performs independent verification and control of EPCs through sampling methods based on issued EPCs (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022).

2.7 Denmark

The Danish Energy Agency is the Authority controlling and monitoring the quality of the EPCs. A random selection of the issued EPCs is controlled to ensure that they meet the set regulations (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022). The control level applied is synonymous with the level c, and it includes site visits in some cases (Gokarakonda *et al.*, 2020). In 2019, Denmark changed their method of assessing the quality of EPCs

from a random selection to a risk-based approach. The new approach uses the lodged EPC certificates and the inputs used in calculations to identify potentially faulty EPCs based on input parameters.

2.8 Greece

The Ministry of Energy performs random checks on the lodged EPCs on the central registry. Validation of input data and calculations is performed at a level c. If necessary, an on-site validation is also performed to verify the data used for the EPC calculation. (Androutsopoulos and Giakoumi, 2022; Fueyo and Herrando, 2022).

2.9 Malta

The Building and Construction Authority (BCA) has designated The Malta Competition and Consumer Affairs Authority as the independent entity in charge of controlling the quality of a sample of Energy Performance Certificates. The sample size is established by taking the total number of EPCs registered in a given year, with a confidence level of 95% and a confidence interval of 5. The sampling plan is designed so that the number of EPCs to be audited is weighted as proportionally as possible to the number of EPCs issued yearly by every assessor (BCA, no date). Malta applies a level c control scheme and includes site visits where necessary (Gokarakonda *et al.*, 2020).

2.10 Poland

An independent body is in charge of checking the quality of EPCs. The items checked include calculation results, compliance of technical systems and U-values with the minimum requirements, energy demand indicators, energy consumption and recommendations, correctness of description, etc. (Kaczorek and Bekierski, 2020).

2.11 Slovenia

C-level controls, including checking input data, calculation results and recommendations, are applied to a statistically significant sample of issued EPCs. These controls are performed by the Inspectorate of the Republic of Slovenia on behalf of the Ministry of the Environment and Spatial Planning (Zavrl *et al.*, 2022).

2.12 Spain

The quality control bodies are appointed regionally. In each region, the relevant institution (Autonomia) is in charge of performing verification and control of EPCs on a sample of EPCs issued each year. Different forms of verification are applied to the selected EPCs, either the validity of the building data used is verified, or a complete verification of the obtained results, recommendations and in situ visit to the building is carried out (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022).

2.13 United Kingdom

In the UK, accreditation schemes are responsible for monitoring the quality of the EPCs by auditing a sample of assessments. Audits are performed by a team of expert assessors with specialist technical expertise. These audits mainly include periodic and non-periodic random audits, audits on new assessors, and audits due to complaints. A minimum of 2% of all EPCs (excluding Level 5 EPCs) are randomly selected for auditing by the Accreditation Schemes. Any audit failures, i.e. out-of-range values, will automatically trigger a requirement for the assessor to withdraw the faulty certificate from the EPC register and re-lodge

a corrected version. It will also trigger a request for a further certificate to be submitted for a targeted audit (Ministry of Housing, Communities and Local Government, 2021). In addition, The Department for Levelling Up, Housing and Communities performs audits twice a year (one scheduled, one on the spot) to increase the data quality. In Scotland, accreditation schemes should check the certificates issued by active assessors at least every six months. If an assessor produces five or fewer certificates within a six-month period, the checking period may be extended to at least every 12 months. The certificates created by all new assessors are checked during the first month of active membership.

The following checks are carried out during the quality checks:

- a. The assessor is certifying within their level of declared competence
- b. Sufficient evidence is recorded to allow assessment of the building
- c. Accuracy of the recorded information
- d. Sufficient data in the building model,
- e. 95% of randomly sampled EPCs must be within a set percentage accuracy compared to an independent assessment of the same building using the evidence contained in assessor records (The Scottish Government, 2012; Ministry of Housing, Communities and Local Government, 2021; CIBSE, 2024).

3 Significant factors

This section highlights the important factors in EPC assessment methodologies that have an impact on the quality of EPCs and therefore should be considered in quality control mechanisms.

3.1 EPC software

The EPC calculation methodologies are implemented in software in all crossCert countries as required by the EPBD (EPBD, 2018). The characteristics of these software can impact the potential mistakes and errors made by assessors and, in turn, affect the quality of the EPC certificates. While countries including Bulgaria, Croatia, Denmark, Greece, Malta, Spain and the UK have official software based on their national EPC calculation methodology, others use commercial software for EPC calculations. Whether these commercial software are accredited by the relevant authority to comply with the national calculation methodology and the EPBD guidelines is an essential factor in the quality control of EPCs. While most countries only allow accredited software for issuing EPCs, some exceptions exist. For example, in Poland, there is no recommended software for the EPC calculation, and there are no requirements for the software to comply with the methodology (EN ISO 13790). Therefore, assessors use various software with different capabilities and sometimes even calculate EPCs manually, which increases the possibility of calculation errors.

3.2 EPC calculation methodology

Another factor that could lead to potential errors is the complexity of the software or the methodology. As highlighted in crossCert Deliverable 3.1 (Sayfekar and Jenkins, 2022), some methodologies (e.g. Bulgaria) are more complex and require multiple steps. In the Bulgarian methodology, the calculated annual final energy consumption needs to be calibrated against the measured annual energy consumption in the building. Then, in order to determine the EPC rating, the calibrated energy consumption is "normalised" (if necessary) so that the basic parameters of the indoor microclimate meet the norms for the respective type of building. Another example is the EPC software in Croatia, which is more complicated when it comes to the HVAC system parameters. Since it doesn't allow the user to define the HVAC system as a whole, it can lead to confusion for some assessors. Some EPC software calculate the U-values of the building envelope automatically, whereas others rely on the assessors to perform the calculations separately. This is the

case in Bulgaria and the methodology for residential buildings in Malta, for which no database is implemented in the national software. Assessors must calculate U-values separately using information from other official resources and enter the results into the software. Such methodologies rely more on the assessors than simpler ones and require highly trained and qualified assessors with the necessary background knowledge.

The higher complexity level of methodologies increases the need for manual checks by experts, particularly for lower-qualified assessors. To ensure higher-quality certificates, manual targeted and randomised checks by independent experts should be in place for these methodologies.

The number of calculation inputs and how they are gathered also affect potential mistakes and errors during assessments. Some methodologies require detailed information about the building envelope and systems, whereas others embed default values for lesser-known parameters to avoid too many discrepancies. Loncour and Roelens (2015) compared EPC methodologies across the European Union, the results showed that the number of inputs across the calculation methodologies in these countries varied between 20 to 500 input values. During the cross-testing phase of the crossCert project, such differences were highlighted through C and L-building reports (Gómez and Fueyo, 2022). An example is the detailed inputs in the Slovenian software regarding the heating system where the assessor should provide the heating power and efficiency at 30% operation and the heat loss in the standby mode, in addition to the commonly required information, including efficiency parameters such as the Coefficient of Performance (COP), Energy Efficiency Ratio (EER), and Seasonal Energy Efficiency Ratio (SEER). Another example is the requirement to enter the length of the pipes or the thickness of pipe insulation in the Austrian software. Most assessors don't have access to such information, which leads to using assumptions that could lead to inconsistent results.

As discussed in more detail in the crossCert D3.1 report (Sayfekar and Jenkins, 2022), some EPC calculation methodologies are more standardised than others. These methodologies tend to provide more default values and schedules for each building type. In contrast, the more tailored methodologies rely on the inputs the assessor provides (whether based on on-site measurements, manufacturer data, or their professional judgement and experience). While relying on the assessor to collect the majority of parameters needed in the assessment could lead to a model that represents the assessed building more accurately, it increases the possibility of errors or using wrong assumptions. When working with methodologies that require a high number of inputs and are more tailored to the assessed building, it's essential to ensure that the collected data is accurate. While implementing validation rules in the software can be helpful, manual checks are also necessary. For such methodologies, it's recommended that automatic checks be implemented in the software to ensure the input data falls within valid ranges. However, manual targeted checks should also be done to ensure the collected data reflects the actual building.

3.3 Assessor background education and training

An essential factor in the quality of EPCs is assessor qualifications and regular training. Higher qualifications and regular training for assessors can lead to higher quality of the produced EPCs and potentially reduce errors made by assessors due to a lack of knowledge. In particular, regular training could help the assessors stay updated with the latest technology and regulations and, therefore, avoid mistakes when the methodology is updated or new technologies such as heat pumps are widely used.

The EPBD does not prescribe any specific regulations for assessor qualifications and training, so every member state devises its own set of requirements for EPC assessors based on the particular needs of its scheme. Although most countries require a certain level of educational background, work experience, and training, there are significant variations among countries. Table 2 provides a summary of each country's requirements. Based on this table, only Slovenia, Croatia, Denmark and the UK have mandatory regular training requirements for the assessors.

Table 2- Summary of training requirements for EPC assessors in chosen European countries

	Minimum education level	Minimum experience required	Additional training	Mandatory regular training
Bulgaria	Engineering degree or technical training	Secondary technical education: 6 years BSc degrees: 3 years, MSc or above degrees: 2 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Level 1 (eligible to issue EPCs for all buildings): must finish a 115-hour course Level 2 (eligible to issue EPCs for residential buildings, low-rise mixed-use buildings and country-house buildings): must finish an 80-hour course. 	-
Poland	Engineering degree		Successfully completing a post-graduate course in engineering and energy auditing or being a licensed engineer. The training course or post-graduate study must include 50 hours of training on certification methodology, calculation, regulations, and assessment of buildings on thermal protection, HVAC and lighting systems.	-
Slovenia	Engineering degree	2 years of experience	A one-week training and passing written and oral exams.	Every 5 years one day training courses
Croatia	Engineering degree	10 years of general experience or 5 years of experience in the design or performance of building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For buildings with simple HVAC systems: successful completion of Module 1 (40 hours) For buildings with complex HVAC systems: successfully completing Module 1 (40 hours) and Module 2 (40 hours) courses. It is mandatory to participate in skills upgrading programs once every year. The courses are only delivered by authorised institutions. 	Annual training
Denmark	Technical training		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No mandatory training before accreditation EPC assessors must pass an exam for various building types. 	Every 3 years

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is mandatory that assessors attend regular (minimum every 3 years) refresher courses 	
Spain	Engineering degree or technical training		No mandatory training.	-
Greece	Engineering degree		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To qualify for assessing Class C buildings, the auditors should pass an exam. No mandatory training 	-
Malta	Engineering degree		No mandatory training	-
Austria	Engineering degree or technical training		No mandatory training	-
UK	No formal requirement	Supervised assessments are often used through training programmes prior to the assessor carrying out assessments independently	25 hours for a Level 3 certificate (27)	Annual training- 10 hours per year

Some countries, including Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece, Poland, Malta, and Slovenia, only allow qualified engineers to become EPC assessors. In Spain, individuals with technical vocational education can also become EPC assessors. In Denmark, technical education is required at a minimum European Qualification Framework (EQF) level 4 or higher, with a minimum duration of 3 years.

In Austria, a wider range of technical backgrounds are eligible for issuing EPC certificates, ranging from engineers to timber constructors, chimney sweepers (only for existing residential buildings, with the exception of new buildings and refurbishments requiring a building permit), and stove fitters (only for detached and semi-detached houses) (28,29). The UK has fewer formal requirements for educational background for EPC assessors compared to other studied countries, and the assessors don't need prior experience or education to train as energy assessors. This is particularly true for residential EPC assessments, as there is a considerable difference in the complexity levels of residential assessments compared to those of non-residential buildings.

As emphasised in other publications, it isn't easy to directly compare the different programmes across the studied countries. However, based on Table 2, Bulgaria, Croatia, Poland, and Slovenia, despite having high requirements regarding background education levels, have the most extended minimum mandatory training programs (40-80 hours) compared to the UK (with around 25 hours) and other countries where there is no mandatory training in place.

It is recommended that targeted quality checks be conducted based on EPC assessors' education and training levels in countries where lower qualification levels are required to become an EPC assessor. This will help better supervise the work of less experienced or trained professionals more prone to errors.

3.4 EPC document

The EPC documents are different across the crossCert countries. Some countries use simple documents with minimum information, such as the EPC rating, annual primary/final energy consumption and CO₂ emissions, mainly targeting users with lower technical knowledge (e.g. building users). Malta, the UK and Denmark fall into this category. Other countries, including Greece, Slovenia, and Croatia, provide more details, including annual energy consumption for heating, cooling, ventilation, lighting, and domestic hot water. Some countries have highly detailed EPCs and provide technical information about the calculation inputs as well as detailed EPC calculation results. Austria, Bulgaria, Poland and Spain are examples of this category.

The type of certificate can impact the quality control measures as it is the primary and most important product of the EPC assessment, and its quality should be ensured for the EPC to fulfil its purpose. Automatic checks can easily check simpler certificates, whereas more complicated and detailed certificates will likely need to be checked manually by experts. Both random and targeted checks are required based on the qualification levels and the production of previous faulty EPCs.

3.5 Energy efficiency recommendations

Another aspect of the methodologies that can play a role in the verification framework is the approach towards energy efficiency recommendations. All countries provide energy efficiency recommendations on their EPCs. As outlined in the crossCert D3.4 deliverable report (Sayfekar and Jenkins, 2024), similar to the standardisation level of calculation methodologies, the countries' approaches to recommendations fall within a spectrum between highly tailored and highly standardised. Some methodologies rely heavily on assessors to suggest measures based on their expertise, whereas others provide assessors with lists of standardised improvement measures for selection or embed them in the EPC software for automatic integration.

While generic advice is less helpful for the building user, it requires fewer quality control measures. Tailored advice highly depends on the buildings and requires manual checks by an experienced and qualified expert. Such measures should depend on the assessor's level of expertise (i.e. targeted checks). However, as it was reiterated in the D3.4 report (Sayfekar and Jenkins, 2024), the educational and training requirements of assessors appear unrelated to these approaches, which may compromise the reliability of advice provided by assessors based on individual experiences and knowledge. Therefore, it is necessary to consider such differences when designing EPC quality control frameworks.

Additionally, the level of detail provided for recommendations and their impacts on energy, carbon emissions, and cost savings differs across countries. Some countries, such as Malta, Poland, and Slovenia, only outline improvement measures without specifying the associated savings amounts, while others (Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Denmark, Greece, Spain and the UK) include such information with varying degrees of detail (Sayfekar and Jenkins, 2024). The calculation methodology of these values varies across countries. In some methodologies (Bulgaria, Malta and Croatia), the assessor manually calculates the savings. In others, the EPC software automatically calculates the savings, thus reducing the assessor's role and potentially reducing possible errors.

Table 3- Summary of countries' approaches to EPC recommendations

Country	Indicators about recommendations on EPC	Default calculation inputs for recommendations	Default list of recommendations	added comments	Savings calculation in software
Austria	energy and carbon emission saving, improved EPC rating, cost savings, investments	✓			✓
Bulgaria	investments, energy and carbon emission savings, and the payback period.		✓	✓	
Croatia	carbon emission saving, improved EPC rating, the payback period		✓		
Denmark	cost savings, investment and carbon emission savings	✓	✓	✓	✓
Greece	Investment, energy, carbon emissions and cost savings, the payback period, improved EPC rating	✓	✓		✓
Malta	-		For non-residential buildings ✓	✓	
Poland	-				
Slovenia	-		✓	✓	
Spain	energy and carbon emissions saving, demand reduction in each energy consumption category, improved EPC rating		✓	✓	✓
UK	improved EPC rating, cost and energy savings, investments	✓	✓		✓

4 Harmonisation of quality control

Similar to the considerable variations between EPC assessments across countries (as highlighted in this report and other crossCert reports), there are differences between the countries' current approaches to quality control. Table 4 summarises these differences. Some countries take advantage of validation rules applied within their EPC software and databases, while others only implement the independent checks required by the EPBD. Interestingly, countries with more standardised methodologies, such as the UK,

Denmark, Austria and Spain, have implemented more automatic controls than more tailored methodologies. This could be a result of a more complicated methodology which requires manual checks by experts rather than automatic checks.

Table 4- current approaches in quality control in crossCert countries

	Standardisation rating (1-highly tailored, 5-highly Standardised)	Software validation rules	Database automatic controls	Organisations in charge of independent checks
Austria	5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A list of errors and explanations about them. • No warnings about out-of-range values 	In some regions in Austria, the EPC database is used for independent quality checks	Performed by relevant energy agencies
Bulgaria	1	Some of the input fields have limits, but the allowed range is wide	Not automatically checked; however, the certificates are checked by the relevant authority before being lodged on the database	SEDA
Croatia	4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are some checks on inputs and results. • No warnings about out-of-range values 	There are no quality controls on the EPC database	The Ministry of Physical Planning, Construction and State Assets
Denmark	4	Input parameter validation measures	The EPC database is equipped with automatic data validation. It is automatically compared with other building data.	The Danish Energy Agency
Greece	4	Input parameter validation measures	Automatic validity check of EPC data is performed on the national EPC registry platform.	The Ministry of Energy
Malta	5	Input parameter validation measures	The data is thoroughly checked and cleaned before being lodged	The Malta Competition and Consumer Affairs Authority (designated

				by the Building and Construction Authority (BCA))
Poland	2	No validation measures	The EPC registry automatically checks for missing data; however, there are no automatic checks for the validity of EPC data.	An independent body
Slovenia	3	Input parameter validation measures	The electronic EPC registry runs an automatic check on the EPC certificates	The Inspectorate of the Republic of Slovenia on behalf of the Ministry of the Environment and Spatial Planning
Spain	4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited validation measures (mostly focused on missing inputs for the technical systems) are implemented, No warnings about out-of-range values. 	Some automatic checks including various identifiers, date of issue, the length of time between the site visit and EPC issue date, useful area, energy rating typology and negative final energy values	Varies regionally, the relevant institution (Autonomia) In each region
UK	5	Highlights out-of-range values	In-built validation rules applied: use of accredited software, missing fields, out-of-range values, parameter formats, consistency, and controlling the trends of data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accreditation Schemes The Department for Levelling Up, Housing and Communities

With efforts focused on harmonising EPC assessments across Europe, quality control mechanisms will need to move in the same direction. However, considering all the differences mentioned, any quality control mechanism needs to be able to address variations in assessment methodologies and adapt to each country's specific needs. Figure 1 shows a framework for adapting quality control mechanisms to an EPC methodology, taking into consideration each aspect discussed in this report. Based on this framework, the quality control mechanism should depend on the calculation methodology, EPC software, EPC document, and assessor qualifications. These categories reflect that quality control is often (or can be) applied in different ways for different aspects of the overall EPC framework. For standardised calculation methodologies similar to the UK and Austria, it is possible to eliminate a higher level of errors by implementing validation rules in the EPC software, whereas for more tailored methodologies, such as the Bulgarian methodology, where there are several steps to modelling the building, manual checks by experts

might be more critical and should be emphasised. EPC software also plays a role in the quality control mechanism. For countries that allow non-accredited software to be used for issuing EPCs, stricter manual checks by independent experts have a higher priority.

Using automatic checks in the EPC database is an effective way to prevent low-quality EPCs. Implementing automatic checks on lodged EPCs is simpler for countries with less detailed documents. However, more manual in-depth checks can be implemented for countries such as Austria with highly detailed documents, where inputs and outputs of calculations are provided.

As mentioned in this report, assessor education, background, and further training requirements vary across countries. Such differences should also be reflected in quality control mechanisms. Countries with lower qualification requirements for assessors can benefit from targeted controls on assessors with low qualifications and experience levels. In contrast, in countries with a more qualified workforce, random checks can be enough to ensure the reliability of EPCs.

Figure 1- A framework for harmonisation of EPC quality control

Table 5- Harmonised quality control measures based on assessment approaches

Criteria	type	Suggested quality control measures			
Calculation methodology	Standardised	Validation rules in the software			
	Tailored	Validation rules in the software + Manual checks			
EPC software	Only accredited software	Validation rules in the software			
	Any software	Manual checks			
EPC document	Detailed	Automatic checks by the EPC database+ Manual checks			
	Simplified	Automatic checks by the EPC database			
EPC recommendations	Tailored	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Savings calculated</td> <td rowspan="2">Depending on the assessor's qualification/experience → targeted checks</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Savings not included</td> </tr> </table>	Savings calculated	Depending on the assessor's qualification/experience → targeted checks	Savings not included
Savings calculated	Depending on the assessor's qualification/experience → targeted checks				
Savings not included					

	Standard	Savings calculated	Automatic checks by the EPC database+ Depending on the assessor's qualification/experience→targeted checks
		Savings not included	Automatic checks by the EPC database
Assessor qualification	Low requirement	Targeted checks+ Manual independent controls	
	High requirement	Manual independent controls	

5 Conclusion

This report aims to provide a detailed summary of the current mechanisms used for quality checks during EPC procedures and highlights the differences between crossCert countries. Quality checking is seen to take place at several levels from the studied EPC frameworks. Specifically, erroneous or questionable parameters (either inputs or outputs, or both) in EPCs will be highlighted during the use of national accredited software, and/or during the lodgement of an EPC record on a national database. The latter may be supported by sampling (and re-checking) of completed EPCs through an accredited body – though the report discusses how the nature of this organisation can be quite different across the studied countries.

The report also seeks to facilitate the harmonisation of EPC quality check measures across European countries by discussing the aspects of EPC assessment approaches that can have a relationship to the quality check methodologies. In order to achieve this goal, the report suggests a framework that takes into account the differences in EPC calculation methodologies, EPC software, EPC documents, energy efficiency recommendations, and qualifications requirements for EPC assessors. This framework aims to provide a path for harmonising quality control mechanisms across all methodologies. However, in doing so, the report and framework also notes the limitations to quality control harmonisation when faced with such different EPC methodologies, assessor workforces, and general implementation. As with many other aspects of EPCs across Europe, a top-down quality control approach for all EPCs is unlikely to be appropriate; country-specific needs, resources, and objectives will (and should) be part of the process of designing an effective set of quality control procedures.

The report further identifies that the level of standardisation of EPC calculation methodologies across countries can lead to inconsistencies in quality check measures, particularly considering the differences in assessors' qualification requirements. Additionally, the level of detail provided in EPC documents can determine which quality control measure should be prioritised. Furthermore, the report highlights the importance of assessors' qualifications requirements in delivering energy efficiency recommendations, mainly depending on the level of standardisation of recommendations in a methodology. A country's approach to recommendations can help determine which quality control mechanisms are better suited to the needs of their methodology. This report therefore proposes that, through simple mapping of quality control pathways (such as documented here) and a knowledge of underlying EPC procedures in a given country, a suitable choice can be made within that country for choosing a quality control process that complements the EPC approach. For countries with highly standardised EPC assessments, this may be more focussed on genuine errors of EPC lodgement. This is due to such assessments already having higher clarity around, for example, what inputs should be used for a particular building type. For assessments that allow for a higher degree of assessor inference, this level of harmonisation and simple quality-checking would be more difficult to achieve – but the assessment itself, with less of a binary approach towards inputs, may be designed to allow for this disagreement amongst assessors. In turn, a quality control procedure that is inflexible on selection of EPC input values would not be appropriate in such cases.

Overall, it should be noted that, when attempting to harmonise EPC methodologies and quality check mechanisms across Europe, the current differences in the methodologies and workforce qualifications must be taken into consideration.

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